

Quantum Étale

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$$q = \bigoplus_0^\varepsilon \iota(\hat{q}) \tag{0.1}$$

$$q_{ij} = (q_i \star q_j) \bigotimes_0^\varepsilon (q_j \star q_i) \tag{0.2}$$

$$\forall i, j \quad \exists q_{ij} \in U_q(\mathbb{E}) \tag{0.3}$$

Let $\gamma : q_{ij} \longrightarrow q^{ij}$ be an arc in a $\mathbf{Top}$ -enriched Fukaya category. Write

$$Pen_q = 2^p \pi \theta \gamma \tag{0.4}$$

for the Lefschetz pencil compatible with q . By “compatible,” it is meant that Pen_q as a pre-sheaf has a gluing condition compatible with the cycle rule for quanta. So, if we have quanta q_{ij} and q_{jk} , we have $q_{ij} \bigcap_0^\varepsilon q_{jk} = q_{ik} \pm \varepsilon \delta_i(\mu(q))$.

1 Transport

Each of the intersecting rays emitted by a Schreiber-type probe give rise to an *ideolectic instantiation*:

$$\mu(q \cap \vec{r}) = \iota(\tilde{q}) \tag{1.1}$$

where $\tilde{q} \simeq \hat{q}_{ij} = q_{Pre}$ is a finite region of a prequantum line and $\vec{r} \in [0, \infty) \times Orb_q$.

Transport is defined to be degenerate if, for two maps $f : \iota(\tilde{q}) \longmapsto [\tau]_\alpha(q)$ and $g : \iota(\tilde{q}) \longmapsto [\tau]_\beta(q)$, we have that $\alpha \equiv \beta$, so that $h : f \xrightarrow{\sim} g$ is an isomorphism. If a kinematic system $\mathcal{K}$ has only degenerate transportation¹, we call it a degenerative system. We write $\mathcal{K}_{Triv}$ for such a system, as it is the one which gives rise to logical trivialism; i.e. the claim that all facts are equally true. A fact such as “I’m right here” is trivial, because it is true regardless of where one is positioned; meanwhile, a fact such as “I am standing” may be more or less true based upon the configuration of one’s body at a given moment of time.

¹See [1] and [2] for reference on these.

1.1 Sheaves of Truth Values

Let $\mathbb{S}^p$ be a spherical manifold, and define the inclusion $\mathbb{S}^p \hookrightarrow \mathbf{Top} \times \mathbf{SF}$ where $\mathbf{SF}$ is Seidel’s classical Fukaya category.² Let Pen_q be a Lefschetz pencil, as above. For the uninitiated, this is a pencil of symplectic hyperplanes on a formally contact copy of $\mathbb{R}^{2n+1}$.

We can smash

$$\mathbb{S}^p \bigwedge_0^P Pen_q \tag{1.2}$$

to form a sheaf $\mathcal{O}_{Hancock}$ making sure that for every $p_\alpha^\beta \in P$, there is a compatible Baez intertwiner ι such that we have $\iota_{\alpha_i}^{\beta_j}(p) = \delta_i(p + \delta_j(p))$ when $j \neq i$. We then have

$$|p| : \iota_{\alpha_i}^{\beta_j}(p) \longrightarrow \tau(p) \tag{1.3}$$

with $\tau(p) \in \mathcal{O}_{Hancock} \odot \mathbb{E}$, where the operator $\odot$ is defined by

$$\mathcal{S} \odot \mathcal{F} = \mathcal{S}_{\sup(\mathcal{F})}^{-\frac{p}{t^3}} \bigoplus_{\Gamma_x^y(\wp(P))} \overline{\mathcal{F}_{\sup(\mathcal{S})}^{(t^3) - Id_{\inf(\mathbb{F})}}}} \tag{1.4}$$

If the class $[\tau]$ of truth values is presentable, then the values are mapped to the smash product of an agent with a fact, which for our purposes we will call the Gardner instantiation.³

A References

- [1] R.J. Buchanan, *Anisotropy of Factions*, (2023)
- [2] R.J. Buchanan, *Quantization and Semiotics*, (Draft)
- [3] R.J. Buchanan, P. Emmerson, O. Hancock, *On the mechanics of quasi-quanta realization*, (2023)

²It is amusing, although only incidental, that *SF* is the abbreviation Paul Erdős used for God; i.e. “supreme Fascist.” It also happens to stand for San Francisco, which is equally irrelevant but somewhat less amusing. Also, Gromov used *TOP* to mean “topological overlapping property.” This can be read more about in Irit Dinur’s 4th lecture on (co)homology entitled “Cohomological Expansion.”

³I name this affectionately after my collaborator J. Gardener, whose work on habits and museum theory is very progressive.